

Combining Histology, Medical imaging and molecular data for medical prognosis and diagnosis: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Combining Histology, Medical imaging and molecular data for medical prognosis and diagnosis

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

CHIMERA

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

CHIMERA(Combining Histology, Medical imaging (radiology) and molecular data for medical prognosis and diagnosis) aims to advance precision medicine in cancer care by addressing the critical need for multimodal data integration. However, integrating various modalities across clinical departments remains a complex challenge. Clinicians face large, heterogeneous datasets that are difficult to analyze effectively. Artificial Intelligence (AI) plays a crucial role in solving this problem, yet many technical barriers remain unsolved, including unifying multimodal data, defining appropriate fusion stages, and addressing challenges where data from one modality is missing. This challenge introduces a benchmark that combines genomics, pathology, and radiology data from multiple institutions to develop AI models. Previous research and challenges have focused on isolated modalities training AI single types of medical data. While effective treatment planning needs a holistic approach that bridges departments and integrates diverse data sources. The rise of foundation models powered by transformer architectures presents opportunities to encode large images, such as pathology and radiology data, into meaningful encodings. This makes it the ideal time to develop a multimodal benchmark that integrates genomics, pathology, and radiology. The proposed challenge includes datasets from prostate and bladder cancer, the multimodal data is collected from multiple centers focused on predicting recurrence in prostate and non-invasive bladder cancer.

Prostate cancer prognosis is currently assessed using PSA levels, a biomarker that remains controversial and is unable to predict biochemical recurrent reliably[1,2]. This challenge aims to predict recurrence by integrating multiparametric MRI and H&E-stained; histopathology slides, two modalities routinely applied in the clinic for initial screening and Gleason grading. Recent studies have shown that deep learning can uncover finer morphological features from histopathology, which hold significant prognostic value in recurrence prediction[3]. The second cancer type included in this challenge is non-invasive bladder cancer (NIBC). A standard treatment for NIBC is the Bacillus Calmette-Guérin (BCG) vaccine, a globally scarce resource. Unfortunately, approximately 50%

of patients receiving BCG fail to respond to the treatment, with unresponsiveness typically identified only during follow-up evaluations, leading to delayed cystectomy. This uncertainty in treatment response complicates patient management, delays effective treatment, and leaves patients with side effects of unnecessary treatment. Recent trials demonstrated that classifying the molecular RNA analysis correlates with a high risk of response. These findings highlight the potential of integrating genomics, pathology, and imaging to improve prognostic accuracy and optimize treatment strategies[4].

The CHIMERA challenge will bring together six participating centers, Radboud University Medical Center (Radboudumc), Erasmus University Medical Center, Canisius Wilhelmina Hospital(CWZ), Isala Zwolle Academie, Brigham University and Stanford University to deliver benchmark AI solutions for recurrence prediction. CHIMERA represents a critical step toward realizing multimodal precision medicine by interoperability between domains and leveraging diverse clinical datasets. This effort aligns with the MICCAI society's goal of advancing AI integration into clinical workflows to improve healthcare outcomes globally.

We will offer pre-extracted features from widely used foundation models, including UNI, Virchow, and GigaPath for digital pathology, as well as popular models in radiology[5,6,7]. These features will enable researchers to explore multimodal fusion techniques without requiring extensive computational resources. This approach ensures the challenge remains sustainable and inclusive, providing accessibility to researchers without large GPU resources, even beyond MICCAI.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

multimodal AI, prostate cancer, bladder cancer, recurrence, cancer survival

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

1. Clinically Relevant Focus: This challenge addresses critical tasks in personalized medicine by predicting recurrence in prostate and bladder cancers, directly influencing patient management and treatment strategies.
2. Multimodal Integration: It evaluates how deep learning models can integrate imaging, pathology, and genomic data to predict recurrence, tackling well-known challenges such as inter-departmental data standardization, fusion stage optimization, and managing missing modalities.
3. Benchmarking Fusion Techniques: CHIMERA advances the field by addressing unresolved technical challenges, including determining optimal fusion stages, handling incomplete data, and ensuring model generalizability.
4. Pre-Extracted Features: By offering pre-extracted features from foundational models like UNI (for pathology) and established radiology models, the challenge reduces computational demands. This sustainable approach ensures inclusivity, allowing participation from researchers with limited GPU resources.
5. Multicenter Collaboration: With datasets from five leading institutions, the challenge ensures diversity and representativeness, providing a robust foundation for model benchmarking.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Prostate Cancer Biochemical Recurrence Prediction:

Application Scenario: Develop AI models to predict biochemical recurrence in prostate cancer patients post-prostatectomy. This integrates histopathology (H&E; slides) and multiparametric MRI (mpMRI) data, aiming to improve patient stratification and post-surgical monitoring.

Clinical Impact: Supports precision medicine by improving prognostic accuracy and personalizing follow-up treatment.

BCG Response Subtype Prediction for HR-NMIBC:

Application Scenario: Use histopathology slides to predict BCG Response Subtypes (BRS1/2/3) in high-risk non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer (HR-NMIBC). These subtypes guide treatment decisions by identifying patients who might not respond to BCG therapy.

Clinical Impact: Optimizes therapeutic decisions, reducing unnecessary treatments and side effects while prioritizing effective interventions.

Bladder Cancer Recurrence Prediction:

Application Scenario: Create multimodal AI models combining H&E; slides and RNA-seq data to predict recurrence timelines in HR-NMIBC. This approach aims to improve risk stratification and treatment planning.

Clinical Impact: Enhances treatment strategies by integrating molecular and morphological data for a more comprehensive prognosis.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

1. Introduction and Overview (30 minutes):

- o Provide an overview of the challenge objectives, dataset details, and evaluation criteria.
- o Introduce the organizing team and explain logistical details, including the session format and timing.

2. Team Presentations (2 hours):

- o Top teams will present their methods, innovations, and results.
- o Each presentation will last 10–15 minutes, showcasing diverse approaches to the challenge tasks.

3. Poster Session (30 minutes):

- o A dedicated session where participants display their posters.
- o Attendees can connect with presenters to discuss specific methods, results, and ideas in more depth.

4. Awards and Closing Remarks (30 minutes):

- o Announce the winning teams and distribute awards.

o Discuss next steps, including plans for publication and how participants can stay engaged with the challenge outcomes.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

50 teams, testing phase: 10-20 teams

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

An overview paper will be written with the organizing team's members. Each participating team who presented their method at the challenge session is allowed up to three co-authorships. The participating teams are encouraged to publish their results separately elsewhere when citing the overview paper after its publication.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The challenge will be held via grand-challenge.org; thus, participating teams will have a fair computing environment. For the half-day event during the conference, we would need a stable high-speed internet connection, projector, loudspeakers, and a microphone.

TASK 1: Predicting biochemical Prostate cancer recurrence from H&E; slides and/or multiparametric MRI

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Prostate cancer, one of the most prevalent malignancies, affects 1.4 million men annually [8]. Early detection is critical, and multiparametric magnetic resonance imaging (mpMRI) plays a central role in screening, as recommended by the 2019 European Association of Urology (EAU) and UK National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) guidelines [8, 2]. When prostate-specific antigen (PSA) levels exceed a commonly used threshold of >4 ng/mL persistently, biopsies are typically performed to confirm the presence of cancer [10]. For advanced cases, prostatectomy often serves as the primary curative treatment.

The effectiveness of prostatectomy is assessed through PSA monitoring during follow-up care. While the role of PSA in initial screening remains debated [1,2], it is an invaluable biomarker post-surgery, with concentrations typically falling to undetectable levels (<0.1 ng/mL) within 4–6 weeks [11]. However, approximately 30% of patients experience biochemical recurrence, where PSA levels rise again, indicating the resurgence of cancer cells. This recurrence is a critical prognostic marker, often signaling progression to clinical metastases and increased risk of mortality from prostate cancer [12,13,14, 15].

Risk assessment for biochemical recurrence relies on a combination of factors, including the International Society of Urological Pathology (ISUP) grade, PSA levels at diagnosis, and TNM staging criteria [16]. Recent European guidelines categorize patients into low-risk, intermediate-risk, and high-risk groups based on these parameters [10], with a high ISUP grade alone being sufficient to classify patients into intermediate (grade 2/3) or high-risk (grade 4/5) groups. The ISUP grading system, based on Gleason growth patterns [17,18,19,20], categorizes cancer morphology but has limitations, including interobserver variability among pathologists and its reliance on coarse descriptors of tissue features.

Recent advancements in deep learning have demonstrated the potential to predict biochemical recurrence using histopathology slides [3]. Building on this progress, the CHIMERA challenge aims to harness the power of AI to uncover finer morphological features with prognostic value. By integrating data from H&E-stained; histopathology slides, mpMRI, and clinical information, including PSA, age, and Gleason grading, this challenge seeks to develop top-performing deep learning models to predict the time to biochemical recurrence, advancing precision medicine in prostate cancer care.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

prostate cancer, biochemical recurrence, cancer survival, deep learning, multiparametric MRI, pathology, H&E;

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Daan Schouten: Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Sciences, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

Robert Spaans: Department of Urology, Canisius Wilhelmina Hospital, Nijmegen, The Netherlands and Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Sciences, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

Khrystyna Faryna: Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Sciences, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

Nadieh Khalili: Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Sciences, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

Geert Litjens: Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Sciences, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Nadieh.khalili@radboudumc.nl

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025 (if get accepted)

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

chimera.grand-challenge.org [under reconstruction]

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

External data and pre-trained models are permitted in this competition, provided they are freely and publicly accessible under a permissive open-source license. Examples of such licenses include the Creative Commons license (standard), GNU software or documentation license (standard), BSD license, MIT license, or Open Database license. If participants are uncertain whether a specific dataset's license qualifies as permissive, they should consult the challenge organizers for clarification.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 10 teams will be invited to be part of the challenge manuscript. In addition, we are actively seeking sponsorship for awards.

1st Place: Certificate of Excellence and a monetary prize (e.g., €3,000, pending sponsorship).

2nd Place: Certificate of Excellence and a monetary prize (e.g., €2,000).

3rd Place: Certificate of Excellence and a monetary prize (e.g., €1,000)

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

1) All results will be announced publicly through a public leaderboard and each participating team will receive the model validation results after the submission. Only the team that submits the method description paper will be eligible for the final ranking.

2) The organizers encourage publicly available code submissions.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

An overview paper will be written with the organizing team's members. Each participating team who presented their method at the challenge session is allowed up to three co-authorships. The participating teams are encouraged to publish their results separately elsewhere when citing the overview paper after its publication.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>

- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Interested teams must join the CHIMERA challenge at chimera.grand-challenge.org. After the release of the training dataset, they can start developing and training AI models using their private or public computing resources. The teams can submit a trained algorithm (a Docker container) for evaluation on a validation cohort. The team are allowed to participate in one task or multiple. During evaluation, algorithms are executed on the grand-challenge.org platform, their performance is estimated on the hidden tuning cohort, and team rankings are updated accordingly on a live, public leaderboard. The top 10 teams based on validation cohort performance will be invited to submit their algorithm Docker containers for prediction on a testing set. Instructions for submitting AI models encapsulated in Docker containers to the Grand

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will be allowed to validate their results multiple times (up to 5) on a validation set before submitting the final results. This can also help participants ensure the submission is in the correct format. Only the best submission will be counted for the official validation ranking. Only a single test set submission will be allowed to avoid overfitting.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Announcement of challenge's opening: April 10th 2025

- Open for registration: April 10th, 2025
- Training data release: April 10th, 2025
- Validation phase start: July 1st, 2025
- Deadline for test set submission: August 1st, 2025
- Winner and invitation speakers: No later than August 23th, 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The Medical Ethics Committee of Radboud University Medical Center approved this challenge protocol on 5/1/2016, with NO. 20162275. Contact person: Geert Litjens, Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Science, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands; geert.litjens@radboudumc.nl

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation pipeline will be made public and open source after the launch of the challenge. We will provide a GitHub link for the code of evaluation metrics on the challenge website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participants are encouraged to upload their code to Github and share the Github link in the PDF submission file.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There is no explicit sponsoring/funding of the challenge, but we aim to contact technology companies with an interest in the prostate cancer prognosis challenge. Only organizing members of the challenge have access to the test case labels during and after the CHIMERA challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance

- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Prognosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Prediction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of biological males, 50 years old and above who underwent prostatectomy after prostate cancer diagnosis. These patients undergo prostatectomy and have both H&E; and MRI.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of biological males, 50 years old and above who underwent prostatectomy after prostate cancer diagnosis. These patients undergo prostatectomy and have both H&E; and MRI.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Brightfield H&E; stained histopathology and multiparametric MRI

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The histopathology slides (*****.tif format, where ***** stands for subject_id) and the MRIs (*****.mha where ***** stands for subject_id). The annotation would be provided as a .csv file with four columns:

pathology_subject_id, MRI_subject_id, recurrence_event, time_to_recurrence_in_months

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

We will provide PSA, age and Gleason scores for prostate patients.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

H&E; stained histopathology slide of a prostate, MRI of a prostate

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The participating algorithms will be designed to predict the time to biochemical recurrence in months from an H&E-stained; histopathology slide and/or MRI of a prostate.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness,Specificity,Sensitivity,Usability,Applicability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Histopathology Imaging: Acquired using the 3D HISTECH PANNORAMIC 1000 histopathology slide scanner at Radboudumc, Nijmegen and CWZ. **mpMRI Imaging:** Acquired using a Siemens 3T scanner at both Radboudumc, Nijmegen, and CWZ, the Netherlands.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The slides were scanned at a resolution of 0.25 micrometers per pixel. The paired mpMRI images were acquired in the axial plane using a Siemens 3T scanner with a standardized imaging protocol that included T1-weighted imaging for anatomical visualization, ADC maps derived from diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) to assess tissue diffusion characteristics, and DWI sequences with multiple b-values for detecting clinically significant prostate cancer.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The training set originates from Radboud University Medical Center, CWZ and TCGA. The test set was obtained from Radboudumc, CWZ, Isala and Stanford University

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

NA

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases both represent a histopathology slide and mpMRI, including T1-weighted imaging, Diffusion-weighted imaging, and ADC map of a prostate. Training and test cases have a weak annotation representing the recurrence event and the time from prostatectomy to the recurrence of the disease in months.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The dataset consists of +/-90 paired cases of MRI and WSI for training, +/-60paired cases of MRI and WSI for validation , and +/-240 paired cases of MRI and WSI for test.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The external 240 paired WSIs and mpMRI cases are reserved exclusively for testing to ensure a fair evaluation of the participating algorithms' generalizability. The internal dataset has been split into 90 training cases and 60 validation cases, following a commonly used ratio in machine learning literature (e.g., approximately 60% training and 40% validation/test combined).

This design emphasizes the real-world challenge of multimodal learning, where data from multiple modalities (e.g., MRI and WSI) must be effectively integrated despite limited paired training samples. Participants are expected to develop robust unimodal encodings for each modality and leverage these encodings to address multimodal fusion challenges. The limited paired training set reflects the reality in clinical settings, where multimodal datasets are often sparse.

To support unimodal model development, participants can use publicly available datasets, such as PICCAI (with 1,400 mpMRI cases) for MRI-based models and LEOPARD (with 500 H&E; cases) for pathology-based models.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The training data has real-world distribution. Participants should expect data with domain shift/from other institutions in validation and testing. We encourage participants to develop models that generalize well across centers despite domain shifts caused by differences in MRI parameters, staining, and scanners in histopathology. At the same time, we will try to match important characteristics of the development and testing cohorts as much as possible, such as age, Gleason grades, etc

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We will publish 140 cases, including both histopathology slides and multiparametric MRI, specifically curated for this challenge.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

NA

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

NA

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Each slide was resampled to include 0.5, 2.0, 8.0 microns/pixel resolution. Slide packing was used to reduce the slide size. The average slide size is approximately 2.0 GB

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

NA

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Not entire prostate tissue histopathology is available for each case. It is possible that some more aggressive parts that correlate with a higher chance of recurrence were not represented in some cases. Such limitation is a consequence of the histopathology tissue processing routines in labs.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

c-index

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The concordance index (C-index) quantifies the model's ability to provide an accurate ranking of the survival times based on the computed individual risk scores, generalizing the area under the receiver operating curve (AUROC). It is a standard metric for the assessment and comparison of survival/recurrence prediction models.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

: The C-index is a widely used metric for survival analysis which allows taking into account time-to-event information and censored data

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We will exclude the participants who fail to report on the whole testing set.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

for each test case, we will calculate the C-index between the ground truth and the results from the participants across all testing images. The ranking will be based on the C-index value obtained on the test cohort.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

A bootstrap will be performed on the test set to evaluate the variance of the C-index of each team and for statistical comparison of algorithm results.

The log-rank test will be used to assess the significance of Kaplan-Meier statistics. The python SciPy and Scikit-learn libraries will be used for the statistical analyses.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The bootstrap analysis allows us to simulate different sampling of the test set to approximate the variance of the C-index

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

These further analyses will be discussed in a publication after the challenge.

TASK 2: Predicting BCG Response Subtypes (BRS) in High-Risk NMIBC Using H&E-Stained; Histopathology

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer (NMIBC) is a significant clinical challenge, particularly for high-risk patients (HR-NMIBC) who face a 20% risk of progression to muscle-invasive or metastatic disease and a 50–60% chance of mortality within 5 years[21,22]. The standard treatment involves transurethral tumor resection followed by intravesical bacillus Calmette-Guerin (BCG), an attenuated vaccine that is costly, difficult to produce, and currently in global shortage. Despite its efficacy in many cases, BCG treatment fails in approximately 20% of HR-NMIBC patients, leading to tumor progression[23,24]. For patients unresponsive to BCG, guideline-recommended treatment is radical cystectomy, a life-altering procedure with high complication rates that severely impacts quality of life.

Current risk stratification methods rely on clinicopathological parameters and patient cohorts that do not account for BCG-specific outcomes. These stratification systems primarily rely on tumor grade, stage, size, number of tumors, and the presence of carcinoma in situ[22]. However, these models were developed based on older patient cohorts that often did not receive BCG therapy as part of their standard care and fail to integrate modern molecular insights[23,24]. As a result, they inadequately differentiate between patients who will respond well to BCG and those who are likely to fail treatment. This one-size-fits-all approach exposes patients to unnecessary toxicity, delays the right treatment for those who will progress despite BCG, and overtreats those who would not progress with BCG or bladder removal. These limitations highlight the need for improved risk stratification methods that incorporate BCG-specific outcomes and modern molecular data to enable personalized treatment strategies.

Recent research by de Jong et al. identified three transcriptomic subtypes of HR-NMIBC, known as BCG Response Subtypes (BRS1/2/3), derived from RNA-based classification[25]. These subtypes correlate with differential responses to BCG treatment, providing a framework for better understanding patient variability and tailoring therapeutic strategies. Notably, BRS3 tumors exhibit aggressive molecular profiles and carry the highest risk of progression[26]. However, molecular subtyping based on transcriptomic data is time-consuming, requires specialized equipment, and is limited to academic centers. Furthermore, intratumor heterogeneity, where multiple subtypes coexist within a single tumor, reduces the predictive accuracy of bulk sequencing approaches, highlighting the need for faster, more accessible, and more accurate subtyping methods.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

bladder cancer, recurrence, deep learning, pathology, H&E, BCG Response Subtypes

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Bas Dille: Department of NEUROLOGY?, Radboud Institute for Health Sciences, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands, Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Sciences, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

Catherine Chia: Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Sciences, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands. Department of Dermatology, Erasmus University Medical Centre, Rotterdam, the Netherlands. Department of Pathology, Erasmus University Medical Centre, Rotterdam, the Netherlands

Pierpaolo Vendittelli Department of Pathology: Radboud Institute for Health Sciences, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

Tahlita Zuiverloon: Erasmus MC Cancer Institute, Department of Urology, Rotterdam, The Netherlands

Nadieh Khalili Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Sciences, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

Geert Litjens, Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Sciences, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Nadieh.khalili@radboudumc.nl

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

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MICCAI 2025 (if get accepted)

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

chimera.grand-challenge.org [under reconstruction]

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

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c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 10 teams will be invited to be part of the challenge manuscript. In addition, we are actively seeking sponsorship for awards.

1st Place: Certificate of Excellence and a monetary prize (e.g., €3,000, pending sponsorship).

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e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

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1) All results will be announced publicly through a public leaderboard and each participating team will receive the model validation results after the submission. Only the team that submits the method description paper will be eligible for the final ranking.

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- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Announcement of challenge's opening: April 10th 2025

- Open for registration: April 10th, 2025
- Training data release: April 10th, 2025
- Validation phase start: July 1st, 2025
- Deadline for test set submission: August 1st, 2025
- Winner and invitation speakers: No later than August 23th, 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The Medical Ethics Committee of Radboud University Medical Center approved this challenge protocol on 5/1/2016, with NO. 20162275. Contact person: Geert Litjens, Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Science, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands; geert.litjens@radboudumc.nl

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation pipeline will be made public and open source after the launch of the challenge. We will provide a GitHub link for the code of evaluation metrics on the challenge website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participants are encouraged to upload their code to Github and share the Github link in the PDF submission file.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There is no explicit sponsoring/funding of the challenge, but we aim to contact technology companies with an interest in the prostate cancer prognosis challenge. Only organizing members of the challenge have access to the test case labels during and after the CHIMERA challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis

- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Prognosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of individuals diagnosed with high-risk non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer (HR-NMIBC), including both biological males and females aged 18 years and above. These patients should have undergone transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT) and have available histopathology slides (H&E; stained) along with RNA-seq data.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of individuals diagnosed with high-risk non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer (HR-NMIBC), including both biological males and females aged 18 years and above. These patients should have undergone transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT) and have available histopathology slides (H&E; stained) along with RNA-seq data.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Brightfield H&E; stained histopathology

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The histopathology slides (*****.tif format, where ***** stands for subject_id). The annotation would be provided as a .csv file with four columns: pathology_subject_id, BRS value

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

For bladder cancer patients, we will provide age, gender, clinical history, BCG treatment (e.g., number of installations), tumor stage, and grade

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

H&E; stained histopathology slide of a bladder biopsies

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The participating algorithms will be designed to predict the BRS1/2/3 from an H&E-stained; histopathology slide of a bladder.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness,Specificity,Sensitivity,Usability,Applicability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

3D HISTECH PANNORAMIC 1000 histopathology slide scanner

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The slides were scanned at a resolution of 0.5 micrometers per pixel.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The training set originates from Radboud University Medical Center and Erasmus Medical Center. The test set was obtained from Radboud University Medical Center and Brigham University and several anonymous institutes; until obtaining the final confirmation, we will keep the names anonymous.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

NA

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases represent a histopathology slide of a bladder. Training and test cases have a weak annotation representing BRS derived from RNA analysis.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The dataset consists of +/-138 training WSIs, +/-92 validation, and +/-250 test WSIs.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The external 250 WSIs are reserved exclusively for testing to ensure a fair evaluation of the participating algorithms' generalizability. The internal dataset has been split into 138 training cases and 92 validation cases, following a commonly used ratio in machine learning literature (e.g., approximately 60% training and 40% validation/test combined).

This design highlights the real-world challenge of multimodal learning, where data from multiple modalities (e.g., histopathology and transcriptomics) must be effectively integrated despite limited paired training samples. Participants are expected to develop robust unimodal encodings for each modality and address fusion challenges.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The training data has real-world distribution. Participants should expect data with domain shift/from other institutions in validation and testing. We encourage participants to develop models that generalize well across centers despite domain shifts caused by differences in staining and scanners in histopathology. At the same time, we will try to match important characteristics of the development and testing cohorts as much as possible, such as age, grades, etc.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We will publish 138 unpublished cases WSIs of NIBC

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

NA

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

NA

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Each slide was resampled to include 0.5, 2.0, 8.0 microns/pixel resolution. Slide packing was used to reduce the slide size. The average slide size is approximately 1.0 GB

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

NA

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

The area annotated for RNA sequencing does not represent the tissue histopathology available for each case. It is possible that some more aggressive parts that correlate with a higher chance of recurrence were not represented in some cases. Such limitation is a consequence of the histopathology tissue processing routines in labs.

ASSESSMENT METHODS**Metric(s)**

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

F1-score

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The F1 score evaluates the model's classification accuracy at the image level based on molecular analysis, combining precision and recall into a single metric. Additionally, the AUROC is used to assess the global discrimination power of the model across various thresholds. Together, these metrics provide a robust evaluation framework for classification tasks involving biomarker response subtypes (BRS).

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The F1-score is a widely used metric for classification, which combines precision and recall into a single score, making it particularly useful for imbalanced datasets where both false positives and false negatives need to be considered equally.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We will exclude the participants who fail to report on the whole testing set.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

For each test case, we will calculate the F1-score between the ground truth and the results from the participants across all testing images. The ranking will be based on the F1-score value obtained on the test cohort.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

A bootstrap will be performed on the test set to evaluate the variance of the F1-score of each team and for statistical comparison of algorithm results.

The log-rank test will be used to assess the significance of Kaplan-Meier statistics. The python SciPy and Scikit-learn libraries will be used for the statistical analyses.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The bootstrap analysis allows us to simulate different sampling of the test set to approximate the variance of the C-index

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

These further analyses will be discussed in a publication after the challenge.

TASK 3: Predicting bladder cancer recurrence from H&E; slides and/or RNA-seq

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer (NMIBC) is a significant clinical challenge, particularly for high-risk patients (HR-NMIBC) who face a 20% risk of progression to muscle-invasive or metastatic disease and a 50–60% chance of mortality within 5 years[21,22]. The standard treatment involves transurethral tumor resection followed by intravesical bacillus Calmette-Guerin (BCG), an attenuated vaccine that is costly, difficult to produce, and currently in global shortage. Despite its efficacy in many cases, BCG treatment fails in approximately 20% of HR-NMIBC patients, leading to tumor progression[23,24]. For patients unresponsive to BCG, guideline-recommended treatment is radical cystectomy, a life-altering procedure with high complication rates that severely impacts quality of life.

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Recent studies have demonstrated the role of molecular analysis in predicting recurrence, identifying gene signatures associated with recurrent disease and informing decisions on cystectomy. In this task, we are harnessing the potential of multimodal deep learning models where the morphological features from H&E-stained; histology images and RNA sequencing data are infused for advanced stratification and recurrence prediction in bladder cancer. As a multimodal AI challenge, CHIMERA aims to evaluate and benchmark innovative methods that integrate these complementary data types to improve prognostic accuracy and personalized treatment strategies.

Keywords

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bladder cancer, recurrence, molecular subtype prediction, deep learning, pathology, RNA-seq, H&E;

ORGANIZATION

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- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Announcement of challenge's opening: April 10th 2025

- Open for registration: April 10th, 2025
- Training data release: April 10th, 2025
- Validation phase start: July 1st, 2025
- Deadline for test set submission: August 1st, 2025
- Winner and invitation speakers: No later than August 23th, 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The Medical Ethics Committee of Radboud University Medical Center approved this challenge protocol on 5/1/2016, with NO. 20162275. Contact person: Geert Litjens, Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Science, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands; geert.litjens@radboudumc.nl

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation pipeline will be made public and open source after the launch of the challenge. We will provide a GitHub link for the code of evaluation metrics on the challenge website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participants are encouraged to upload their code to Github and share the Github link in the PDF submission file.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There is no explicit sponsoring/funding of the challenge, but we aim to contact technology companies with an interest in the prostate cancer prognosis challenge. Only organizing members of the challenge have access to the test case labels during and after the CHIMERA challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis

- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Prognosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Prediction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of individuals diagnosed with high-risk non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer (HR-NMIBC), including both biological males and females aged 18 years and above. These patients should have undergone transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT) and have available histopathology slides (H&E; stained) along with RNA-seq data.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of individuals diagnosed with high-risk non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer (HR-NMIBC), including both biological males and females aged 18 years and above. These patients should have undergone transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT) and have available histopathology slides (H&E; stained) along with RNA-seq data.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Brightfield H&E; stained histopathology and RNA-seq

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The histopathology slides (*****.tif format, where ***** stands for subject_id) that were collected in different real-life scenarios. The annotation would be provided as a .csv file with four columns: pathology_subject_id, transcriptomics_subject_id, recurrence_event, time_to_recurrence_in_months

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

For bladder cancer patients, we will provide age, gender, clinical history, BCG treatment (e.g., number of installations), tumor stage, grade, and we will provide RNA-seq

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

H&E; stained histopathology slide of a bladder and RNA-seq of tumor area

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The participating algorithms will be designed to predict the time to recurrence in months from an H&E; stained histopathology slide and RNA-seq of a bladder

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that

assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Robustness, Specificity, Sensitivity, Usability, Applicability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

3D HISTECH PANNORAMIC 1000 histopathology slide scanner, DESeq2, 20000 gene

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The slides were scanned at a resolution of 0.5 micrometers per pixel.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The training set originates from Radboud University Medical Center and Erasmus Medical Center. The test set was obtained from Radboud University Medical Center and Brigham University and several anonymous institutes; until obtaining the final confirmation, we will keep the names anonymous.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

NA

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases both represent a histopathology slide of a bladder and RNA-seq of the tumor area.

Training and test cases have a weak annotation representing the recurrence event to the recurrence of the

disease in months.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The dataset consists of +/-138 paired WSIs and RNA-seq, +/-92 validation, and +/-250 test paired of WSIs and RNA-seq.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The external paired 250 WSIs and RNA-seq are reserved exclusively for testing to ensure a fair evaluation of the participating algorithms' generalizability. The internal dataset has been split into 138 training cases and 92 validation cases, following a commonly used ratio in machine learning literature (e.g., approximately 60% training and 40% validation/test combined).

This design highlights the real-world challenge of multimodal learning, where data from multiple modalities (e.g., histopathology and transcriptomics) must be effectively integrated despite limited paired training samples. Participants are expected to develop robust unimodal encodings for each modality and address fusion challenges.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The training data has real-world distribution. Participants should expect data with domain shift/from other institutions in validation and testing. We encourage participants to develop models that generalize well across centers despite domain shifts caused by differences in staining and scanners in histopathology. At the same time, we will try to match important characteristics of the development and testing cohorts as much as possible, such as age, grades, etc.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We will publish 138 unpublished cases of paired WSIs and RNA-seq of NIBC

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

NA

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

NA

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Each slide was resampled to include 0.5, 2.0, 8.0 microns/pixel resolution. Slide packing was used to reduce the slide size. The average slide size is approximately 1.0 GB

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

NA

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

The area annotated for RNA sequencing does not represent the tissue histopathology available for each case. It is possible that some more aggressive parts that correlate with a higher chance of recurrence were not represented in some cases. Such limitation is a consequence of the histopathology tissue processing routines in labs.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

c-index

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The concordance index (C-index) quantifies the model's ability to provide an accurate ranking of the survival times based on the computed individual risk scores, generalizing the area under the receiver operating curve (AUROC). It is a standard metric for the assessment and comparison of survival/recurrence prediction models.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The C-index is a widely used metric for survival analysis which allows taking into account time-to-event information and censored data.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We will exclude the participants who fail to report on the whole testing set.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

For each test case, we will calculate the C-index between the ground truth and the results from the participants across all testing images. The ranking will be based on the C-index value obtained on the test cohort.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

A bootstrap will be performed on the test set to evaluate the variance of the C-index of each team and for statistical comparison of algorithm results.

The log-rank test will be used to assess the significance of Kaplan-Meier statistics. The python SciPy and Scikit-learn libraries will be used for the statistical analyses.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The bootstrap analysis allows us to simulate different sampling of the test set to approximate the variance of the C-index

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

These further analyses will be discussed in a publication after the challenge.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

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Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A